

Clinicopathological Profile of Nasopharyngeal Carcinoma

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Abstract:

This observational study conducted at SCB Medical College and Hospital, Cuttack, Odisha, explored the clinicopathological profile of nasopharyngeal carcinoma (NPC) from July 2019 to September 2022. Focusing on 30 patients, the study revealed a higher prevalence of NPC among males with the majority of cases falling in the 30-50 age group. Non-keratinizing carcinoma was the most common histological type observed, emphasizing the significant role of Epstein-Barr virus (EBV) in the pathogenesis of NPC. Key clinical presentations included neck swelling and epistaxis, which are symptomatic of advanced stages. The study highlighted the impact of environmental factors such as tobacco use and consumption of salted smoked fish, aligning with known risk factors. These findings underscore the necessity for early screening, particularly in high-risk populations, and advocate for public health strategies focusing on lifestyle modifications. The study's implications for enhancing NPC management through tailored interventions and the need for larger studies to further explore these associations are discussed.

Keywords: Nasopharyngeal Carcinoma, Epstein-Barr Virus, Risk Factors, Non-Keratinizing Carcinoma.

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Introduction

Nasopharyngeal carcinoma (NPC) is an intriguing and distinct type of cancer that arises from the epithelial cells of the nasopharynx, which is the region behind the nose and above the back of the throat [1]. Characterized by its unique epidemiological pattern, NPC shows a markedly high incidence in Southeast Asia and Southern China, particularly in the Guangdong province, earning it the nickname "Guangdong tumor". Contrastingly, it is relatively rare in Western countries [2]. The disease's prevalence in certain regions, such as the North-Eastern states of India like Manipur and Nagaland, underscores the influence of regional dietary habits and genetic backgrounds on its incidence [3].

The etiology of NPC involves a complex interplay of genetic factors, environmental influences, and the ubiquitous association with Epstein-Barr virus (EBV), particularly in non-keratinizing types of NPC. Environmental factors, including the consumption of nitrosamine-rich salted fish, a common dietary practice in high-incidence areas, play a significant role in its pathogenesis [4]. Clinically, NPC often remains unnoticed until

advanced stages due to its deep location, which complicates early detection. Symptoms, when they occur, typically include a neck mass, nasal obstruction, and hearing issues related to otitis media with effusion from eustachian tube dysfunction. Diagnosis is generally achieved through advanced imaging techniques such as MRI and CT scans, supported by histopathological examination [5].

Histologically, NPC is categorized into keratinizing squamous cell carcinoma and the more prevalent non-keratinizing carcinoma, which is subdivided into differentiated and undifferentiated types [6]. The latter is closely linked to EBV and is known for its aggressive nature and propensity to metastasize. Understanding the clinicopathological profile of NPC, with its distinct regional and racial disparities, is vital for devising effective screening methods and treatment protocols that are tailored to the specific genetic and environmental context of affected populations.

Methodology

Study Design: The study was designed as an observational study conducted at a tertiary care center's ENT department. It aimed to assess the clinicopathological profile of nasopharyngeal carcinoma, including demographic data, clinical presentation, histopathological characteristics, and treatment outcomes.

Study Setting: The research was carried out in the ENT Department of SCB Medical College and Hospital, Cuttack, Odisha. This setting was chosen due to its high patient influx and established facilities for managing complex cases like NPC, providing a diverse sample for meaningful insights.

Duration of the Study: The study spanned from July 2019 to September 2022. This period allowed for the accumulation of sufficient data to ensure statistical relevance and depth in the findings related to the varied presentations and outcomes of NPC.

Participant Selection

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients admitted to the institute with a nasopharyngeal mass clinically or radiologically suspected to be nasopharyngeal carcinoma.
- Patients who provided informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients in a chronic debilitated state who could not undergo the standard diagnostic and treatment protocols.
- Patients who did not give consent for participation.

Data Collection Methods

Data collection involved several steps:

- **Initial Assessment:** Patients underwent a detailed history taking and a thorough clinical examination to assess symptoms and physical signs of NPC.
- **Diagnostic Assessment:** Included nasal endoscopy, imaging studies such as X-rays of the nose and paranasal sinuses, CT scans, and MRI when needed to confirm the diagnosis and stage of the disease.
- **Histopathological Examination:** Biopsies were taken from suspected nasopharyngeal masses and analyzed to confirm the diagnosis of NPC.
- **Treatment and Follow-up Data:** Information on treatment modalities, including radiation and chemotherapy, as well as follow-up data on patient outcomes, was collected.

Data Recording: All data were meticulously recorded in a specially designed case record form,

ensuring completeness and accuracy. This included demographic details, clinical features, diagnostic findings, treatment regimens, and follow-up outcomes.

Results

Participant Demographics

- **Total Participants:** The study evaluated a total of 30 patients diagnosed with nasopharyngeal carcinoma.
- **Age Distribution:** Most patients fell within the 30-50 years age bracket (47%), followed by the 50-70 years group (40%). The mean age was 49.5 years.
- **Gender Distribution:** The study had a higher prevalence of male patients (53%) compared to female patients (47%), with a male-to-female ratio of 1.72:1.
- **Socioeconomic Status:** A significant majority of the patients (96.67%) belonged to the lower socioeconomic classes (Class III to V).

Clinical Presentation

- **Symptoms:** The most commonly reported symptoms were neck swelling and epistaxis, both observed in 86.67% of the patients. Other frequent symptoms included nasal obstruction (40%) and hearing loss (36.67%).
- **Diagnosis:** Diagnosis was primarily confirmed through histopathological examination, with additional imaging studies supporting staging and extent of disease.

Histopathological Findings: Histological Types: Non-keratinizing carcinoma was the predominant histological type observed among the participants. A detailed breakdown of subtypes was not provided in the snippet, but non-keratinizing carcinoma is generally more common in the studied region.

Treatment and Outcomes

- **Treatment Approaches:** The majority of patients were treated with a combination of radiation therapy and chemotherapy, following the standard treatment protocols for advanced stages of NPC.
- **Survival and Prognosis:** Detailed survival rates and long-term outcomes were not specified in the available snippets. However, the treatment adherence and follow-up assessments were noted to be consistent with ongoing clinical support.

Additional Observations

- **Risk Factors:** High consumption of salted smoked fish and tobacco use were noted as prevalent risk factors among the patients, with

63.33% of patients consuming salted smoked fish and 90% using tobacco in various forms.

- Environmental Exposures: Exposure to wood dust and household smoke was also reported,

suggesting occupational and environmental risk factors in the patient population.

These tables organize the key findings of the study on nasopharyngeal carcinoma into a structured format, making the data easily accessible and comprehensible.

Table 1: Participant Demographics and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	Data
Total Participants	30
Age Range	10-85 years
Mean Age	49.5 years
Age Distribution	<30 yrs: 13% 30-50 yrs: 47% > 50 yrs: 40%
Gender Distribution	Male: 53% Female: 47%
Socioeconomic Status	Class II: 3.3% Class III: 23.33% Class IV: 26.67% Class V: 46.67%

Table 2: Clinical Presentation

Symptom	Percentage of Patients
Neck Swelling	86.67%
Epistaxis	86.67%
Nasal Obstruction	40.00%
Hearing Loss	36.67%
Visual Difficulties	33.33%
Stridor	10.00%
Headache	10.00%

Table 3: Risk Factors

Risk Factor	Percentage of Patients
Tobacco Use	90%
Consumption of Salted Smoked Fish	63.33%
Exposure to Wood Dust	10%
Exposure to Household Smoke	30%
Alcohol Intake	33.33%

Table 4: Histopathological Findings

Histological Type	Frequency
Non-Keratinizing Carcinoma	Predominant Type
Keratinizing Squamous Cell Carcinoma	Less Common

Table 5: Treatment Approaches

Treatment Type	Description
Radiation Only	Used for Stage I and II
Concurrent Chemotherapy and Radiation	Used for Stage III and IV

Discussion

The study conducted at Utkal University on the clinicopathological profile of nasopharyngeal carcinoma (NPC) provides significant insights into the disease's demographics, clinical presentation, histopathology, and associated risk factors within a specific regional context in India [8]. The findings underscore the unique epidemiological pattern of NPC, which is predominantly prevalent in Southeast Asia and specific regions of India, aligning with global data that emphasize the geographical disparity in NPC incidence. The demographic distribution, with a higher prevalence among males and most patients falling within the age range of 30 to 50 years, suggests potential hormonal, occupational, and lifestyle influences on disease risk [9].

Clinically, the study highlights the typical late presentation of NPC, with symptoms such as neck swelling and epistaxis prevalent among patients. This pattern is indicative of the anatomical complexity and insidious onset of the disease, which often evades early detection. The reliance on sophisticated imaging and biopsy for diagnosis further points to the necessity for heightened awareness and potentially the development of specific screening protocols in high-risk populations to facilitate earlier diagnosis [10,11].

Histopathologically, the predominance of non-keratinizing carcinoma observed in the study is consistent with the global trend, particularly in endemic regions, and reinforces the central role of the Epstein-Barr virus (EBV) in NPC pathogenesis. This vital link offers promising avenues for targeted therapeutic strategies and preventive measures, including vaccination and antiviral interventions [12,13]. The study also brings attention to significant environmental and lifestyle risk factors, such as high consumption of salted smoked fish and tobacco use. These findings offer actionable insights for public health initiatives aimed at dietary guidance and smoking cessation, which could potentially mitigate the incidence of NPC in high-risk areas [14,15].

However, the study's limitations, including its observational design and relatively small sample size, may affect the generalizability of the findings. Future research should aim to extend these

observations through larger, multicentric studies that could provide more robust data and explore the genetic and molecular underpinnings of NPC [16,17]. Additionally, examining the efficacy of emerging treatment modalities, such as immunotherapy and targeted therapy, could significantly enhance the therapeutic landscape for NPC [18-20].

Conclusion

The study on nasopharyngeal carcinoma (NPC) conducted at Utkal University provides valuable insights into the epidemiological, clinical, and histopathological aspects of NPC within a distinct Indian population. By highlighting the predominance of non-keratinizing carcinoma linked closely with Epstein-Barr virus (EBV) and underscoring the significant impact of environmental and lifestyle factors such as tobacco use and dietary habits, this research emphasizes the need for targeted public health interventions and advanced diagnostic strategies. The findings advocate for the development of regional screening programs and tailored treatment approaches to enhance early detection and improve therapeutic outcomes for NPC. Future research should expand on these findings with larger participant pools to explore the potential of novel therapies and preventive measures, further aiming to reduce the disease burden and improve the quality of life for patients afflicted with NPC.

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